

Copper(II) Complexes of 8-Quinolyldiazonoacetylacetone and 8-Quinolyldiazonocyclohexandione

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In continuation of our studies on arylazo and heteroarylazo derivatives of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes¹, we here report the synthesis and characterisation of 8-quinolyldiazono derivatives of acetylacetone and 1,3-cyclohexandione, and their copper(II) complexes.

Results and Discussion

The quinolyldiazono derivatives of acetylacetone (Hqaa) and 1,3-cyclohexandione are formed in good yields (~90%) by the reaction of quinoline-8-diazonium salt (diazotised 8-aminoquinoline) with the diketones (Table 1). The data are in agreement with the intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded hydrazone form rather than the alternative azo tautomer.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found / (Calcd)			
		C	H	N	M
Hqaa	192	65.30 (65.88)	4.98 5.10	16.15 16.47	
Cu(qaa) ₂	252	57.88 (58.79)	4.11 4.20	14.22 14.70	10.98 11.11
Hqcy	183	66.78 (67.42)	4.56 4.87	14.96 15.73	
Cu(qcy) ₂	300	61.23 (61.70)	3.89 4.11	13.95 14.40	10.48 10.88

Hqaa, R = CH₃
Hqcy, R = CH₂CH₂CH₂

Thus the ir spectrum of Hqaa shows two strong bands at 1 667 and 1 655 cm⁻¹ and two medium intensity bands at 1 628 and 1 620 cm⁻¹. Based on earlier assignments^{2,3} on related compounds, these bands can be assigned respectively to the stretching of free conjugated acetyl carbonyl,

hydrogen-bonded acetyl carbonyl, cyclic C=N and the hydrazone C=N groups. The corresponding bands of Hqcy are observed at 1 685, 1 668, 1 632 and 1 623 cm⁻¹ and are consistent with the reported data of 2-aryl-hydrazone of 1,3-cyclohexandione⁴. The chelated nature of the NH group of the compounds, is evident from the presence of a broad band at 2 500–3 400 cm⁻¹.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the compounds show a low-field one proton signal at about 16.2 ppm. Such a low value for the acidic proton, compared to the hydrazone proton of 2-phenylhydrazone derivatives of acetylacetone^{1,2} and 1,3-cyclohexanedione^{4,5} can be attributed to the involvement of this proton in the bifurcated hydrogen-bonding as in structure 1. That one of acetyl carbonyl groups of Hqaa is involved in hydrogen-bonding is evident from the observed methyl proton signals (δ 2.48, 6H, s; 2.30, 6H, s) of the compound. In the case of Hqcy, the alicyclic proton signals at C-4 and C-6 show separate signals at δ 2.143 (2H, t) and 2.086 (2H, t), indicating the difference in the electronic environment of the two carbonyl groups. As expected of the structure, the C-6 proton signals is a quintuplet at δ 2.781 (2H). The aryl proton signals are observed as a multiplet at δ 8.985–7.518 (6H).

The mass spectra of the compounds showed a prominent parent ion peak (P+1)⁺. Peaks due to (P-CH₃CO)⁺ (*m/z* 212), (P-2CH₃CO)⁺ (*m/z* 170) are typical of the spectra of Hqaa. The most significant feature of the spectra of both the compounds is the presence of peaks at *m/z* 176 and 143 due to the formation of the ions QNH₂CH⁺ and QNH⁺ respectively (Q = 8-quinolyl, C₉H₆NH). The presence of these two peaks and the absence of a (P-N₂)⁺ peak in the spectra of the compounds clearly indicate the hydrazone form rather than the azo form⁶.

The elemental analysis data of the copper(II) complexes show 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry and the complexes behave as non-electrolytes showing magnetic moment of ~ 1.75 B.M.

Ir spectral data of the complexes are in accord with structure 2. Thus the free carbonyl band of the ligand is only marginally shifted. The band due to hydrogen bonded carbonyl functions disappeared and instead a new band ap-

peared at 1565 cm^{-1} in the case of $\text{Cu}(\text{qaa})_2$ and at 1585 cm^{-1} for $\text{Cu}(\text{qcy})_2$ assignable to metal bonded carbonyl function⁷. The band due to cyclic $\text{C}=\text{N}$ shifted appreciably to lower value ($\sim 15\text{ cm}^{-1}$) in complexes indicating that the hetero-nitrogen is involved in bonding with the metal ion. A medium intensity band observed at $\sim 1525\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH deformation) in the spectra of the free ligand disappeared in the spectra of the complexes, presumably due to the replacement of the N-H proton by metal ion as in structure 2. Similarly, a prominent band appearing in the spectra of the ligands at $\sim 1280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-N) shifted to $\sim 1265\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, which is a strong indication of the coordination of the C-N nitrogen with the metal ion. The broad band of the free ligand at $2500\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was absent in the spectra of the complexes and instead revealed the presence of weak bands characteristics of aliphatic and aromatic C-H. Two medium intensity bands at ~ 425 and 530 cm^{-1} observed in the spectra of the complexes can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations^{1,7}.

The FAB mass spectra of the complexes showed intense molecular ion peak corresponding to $(\text{CuL}_2)^+$. Strong peaks due to CuL and Cu_2L_2 were also observed in the spectra. Similarly, several metal-containing fragments corresponding to the natural abundance (2 : 1) of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu can be easily located in the spectra of the complexes.

Experimental

8-Aminoquinoline (0.005 mol) was diazotised⁸. The diazonium salt solution kept below 5° , was added dropwise to a well-cooled ethanolic solution (5 ml) of the 1,3-diketone (0.005 mol). Sodium acetate solution was added to keep pH of the mixture around 7. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from hot ethanol as yellow crystals.

Copper(II) chelates were prepared by mixing a solution of the ligand (0.001 mol in 5 ml methanol) and copper(II) acetate (0.0005 mol in 5 ml methanol). The mixture was heated on a water-bath for ~ 10 min and the resulting green solid was washed with water and then with methanol and dried under reduced pressure.

The IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a PE 983 IR spectrophotometer, NMR spectra on a BRUKER 400 MHz spectrometer and mass spectra on a JEOL/SX-102 spectrometer (FAB using argon and *m*-nitrobenzyl alcohol/glycerol as the matrix).

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